

Deliverable 4.5

Packaged tested version of MT system

Dissemination Level	PU
Due Date of Deliverable	31/12/2021 (M36)
Actual Submission Date	04/11/2021
Work Package	WP4 - Innovations and Data Production
Task	Task 4.2 Preparing tools for the use of Computer Assisted Translation
Type	Other
Approval Status	Waiting EC Approval
Version	V1.0
Number of Pages	p.1 – p.7

Abstract:

This deliverable describes the packaging and release process of the machine translation (MT) systems prepared by CLARIN/CUNI. This document describes the included translation models and the underlying MT framework and their release within the Lindat repository.

The information in this document reflects only the author's views and the European Community is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The information in this document is provided "as is" without guarantee or warranty of any kind, express or implied, including but not limited to the fitness of the information for a particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at his/ her sole risk and liability. This deliverable is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

History

Version	Date	Reason	Revised by
0.0	24/08/2021	initial submission	Carsten Thiel
0.1	27/10/2021	addressing internal peer review	Dušan Variš
1.0	28/10/2021	final version of the document	Dušan Variš

Author List

Organisation	Name	Contact Information
CLARIN/CUNI	Dušan Variš	varis@ufal.mff.cuni.cz

Executive Summary

This document describes the packaging and release of the CUNI machine translation (MT) systems trained within the Tensor2tensor framework for sequence-to-sequence learning that was developed for task T4.5. The MT backend, together with a simple command-line interface (CLI) is released separately from the models. The MT backend is released as a separate Docker image as a platform-independent solution. The compilation of the docker images is separated into two parts: first, a base image containing the Tensor2tensor installation is prepared and second, a language-specific derivative of the base image is compiled for the chosen MT model. The independent release of the MT models also allows the user to download the models separately and execute them using their local Tensor2tensor installation if necessary.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface
CLI	Command-Line Interface
CUNI	Charles University
MT	Machine Translation
T2T	Tensor2tensor
WMT	Workshop on Machine Translation

Table of Contents

Introduction	5
Package Contents	5
Main Package	5
Model Packages	6
Installation	7
REST Server API Description	7
References	7

1. Introduction

This deliverable provides a description of the machine translation (MT) systems prepared by CLARIN/CUNI with details about the packaging and release process. The models developed by CUNI were trained using the Tensor2tensor¹ (T2T, Vaswani et al. 2018) neural sequence-to-sequence framework based on the TensorFlow² (Abadi et al. 2016) deep learning toolkit. The Institute of Formal and Applied Linguistics at CUNI (later referred to as the institute) released the underlying T2T framework using the Docker³ platform allowing platform-independent deployment. The MT models were released separately from the dockerized T2T backend, exported using the TensorFlow Serving serialization, allowing the user to use the models with their own T2T and TensorFlow Serving installation.

The current release supports translation for the following language pairs (in both translation directions): En-Cs, En-De, En-Fr, En-Pl and En-Ru. The models were trained using the corpora available at WMT News Translation Task website.⁴ The En-De and En-Ru models were trained using only the available WMT parallel corpora. En-Cs, En-Fr and En-Pl models were trained using the CUBBITT⁵ (Popel et al. 2020) approach that combines training on the genuine parallel data with the iteratively translated monolingual corpora leading to a recent state-of-the-art performance in the domain of news article translation.

The models and the Docker makefiles for building the Docker image of the MT backend are publicly available in the LINDAT repository.⁶ The institute provides the direct link for model download in the following section. The institute released the dockerized T2T backend under the Apache 2.0 license and the En-De, En-Ru translation models under the CC BY-NC-SA license. The CUBBITT models (En-Cs, En-Fr and En-Ru) were partially developed outside of the SSHOC project and the licensing choice (CC BY-NC-SA license) for these models was not performed by the SSHOC team members.

2. Package Contents

In the following section, the contents of the package containing the dockerized T2T backend and the contents of the MT model release are described in more detail.

Main Package

The main package “Tensor2tensor Translation for Docker” located in the LINDAT repository contains the following files:

¹ Github: <https://github.com/tensorflow/tensor2tensor/> (accessed Oct 2021)

² TensorFlow web: <https://www.tensorflow.org/> (accessed Oct 2021)

³ Docker: <https://www.docker.com/> (accessed Oct 2021)

⁴ <http://statmt.org/wmt21/> (accessed Oct 2021)

⁵ Popel, M., Tomkova, M., Tomek, J. et al. Transforming machine translation: a deep learning system reaches news translation quality comparable to human professionals. Nat Commun 11, 4381 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-18073-9>

⁶ <https://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/repository/xmlui/handle/11234/1-3734> (accessed Oct 2021)

- **README.md** - description of the package including installation guide and sample usage examples
- **LICENSE** - licensing details
- **Dockerfile.build.sh** - a wrapper for the process of building of the Docker image for the backend and downloading the model for the given language pair (single script parameter, requires lower-cased specification of the language pair, e.g. "en-cs")
- **Dockerfile.base** - base image Dockerfile used for setting up the T2T and TensorFlow Serving environment
- **Dockerfile.template** - template for extending the base Docker image with a specific MT model
- **usr_dir/my_registrations.py** - a file containing the T2T-compatible model description with definitions of the model-specific modifications
- **start.sh** - initialization scripts; used for executing the TensorFlow Serving backend and the communication API (t2t-serving-adapter.py) inside the docker container
- **t2t-serving-adapter.py** - REST server adapter used for communication between the frontend (e.g. *translate.sh* CLI, *curl* Unix utility) and the TensorFlow Serving backend. The rest server supports structured HTTP requests in a JSON format (described in Section 4)
- **translate.sh** - an example of a frontend CLI for (unstructured) plaintext translation
- **models/get_models.sh** - script for downloading of the MT models
- **models/available_models.txt** - a list of the LINDAT submission handles for the respective models
- **models/batching.config** - TensorFlow Serving configuration of the batching parameters for the translation
- **models/model.config.gen**, **models/model.config.template** - files for generating model specific TensorFlow Serving configurations

Model Packages

Archives containing the model files are released separately from the main package for the purposes of future versioning. A separate package for each of the En-Cs, En-De, En-Fr, En-Pl and En-Ru language pairs was released, providing the user with a separate model for each translation direction. The models are also available online via LINDAT Translation service.⁷

Each model archive contains the following files:

- **export/** - directory containing the TensorFlow Serving compatible model serialization
- **vocab.encs.32768** - decoding vocabulary for the model (note that the "encs" naming convention is based on the similar model definition during training of different models; the En-Cs template was also used for the other translation models)

The model archives are available under the following URLs:

- En-Cs model: <https://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/repository/xmlui/handle/11234/1-3733>
- En-De model: <https://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/repository/xmlui/handle/11234/1-3732>

⁷ LINDAT Translation: <https://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/services/transformer/> (Accessed Oct 2021)

- En-Fr model: <https://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/repository/xmlui/handle/11234/1-3743>
- En-Pl model: <https://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/repository/xmlui/handle/11234/1-3742>
- En-Ru model <https://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/repository/xmlui/handle/11234/1-3744>

3. Installation

Please refer to the *README.md* file inside the main package for details about the MT backend installation.

4. REST Server API Description

Although the institute provides a simple CLI for communicating with the backend REST server inside the docker container, they also provide the information about the REST server API to allow the user to create their own frontend if necessary.

The REST server API is based on the machine translation API defined in the Deliverable D4.1⁸ of the European Language Grid project.⁹ Please refer to Section 6 of the respective deliverable for more details.

5. References

- Abadi, Martín, Ashish Agarwal, Paul Barham, Eugene Brevdo, Zhifeng Chen, Craig Citro, Greg S. Corrado, Andy Davis, Jeffrey Dean, Matthieu Devin, Sanjay Ghemawat, Ian Goodfellow, Andrew Harp, Geoffrey Irving, Michael Isard, Yangqing Jia, Rafal Jozefowicz, Lukasz Kaiser, Manjunath Kudlur, Josh Levenberg, Dan Mane, Rajat Monga, Sherry Moore, Derek Murray, Chris Olah, Mike Schuster, Jonathon Shlens, Benoit Steiner, Ilya Sutskever, Kunal Talwar, Paul Tucker, Vincent Vanhoucke, Vijay Vasudevan, Fernanda Viegas, Oriol Vinyals, Pete Warden, Martin Wattenberg, Martin Wicke, Yuan Yu, and Xiaoqiang Zheng. 2016. "TensorFlow: Large-Scale Machine Learning on Heterogeneous Distributed Systems." *ArXiv:1603.04467 [Cs]*.
- Popel, Martin, Marketa Tomkova, Jakub Tomek, Łukasz Kaiser, Jakob Uszkoreit, Ondřej Bojar, and Zdeněk Žabokrtský. 2020. "Transforming Machine Translation: A Deep Learning System Reaches News Translation Quality Comparable to Human Professionals." *Nature Communications* 11(1):4381. doi: 10.1038/s41467-020-18073-9.
- Vaswani, Ashish, Samy Bengio, Eugene Brevdo, Francois Chollet, Aidan N. Gomez, Stephan Gouws, Llion Jones, Łukasz Kaiser, Nal Kalchbrenner, Niki Parmar, Ryan Sepassi, Noam Shazeer, and Jakob Uszkoreit. 2018. "Tensor2Tensor for Neural Machine Translation." *ArXiv:1803.07416 [Cs, Stat]*.

⁸ D4.1 Services, Tools and Components (first release) (USFD) available here: <https://www.european-language-grid.eu/deliverables/> (accessed Oct 2021)

⁹ The European Language Grid has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme; Grant agreement № 825627 (ELG)